

WORK ON TEXT IN PRIMARY SCHOOL

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Priority 4 of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev dated February 7, 2017 No. PF-4947 "Strategy of Action" is aimed at "Development of the social sphere." Section 4.4 of the program is entitled "Development of education and science", which includes further improvement of the system of continuing education, increasing the capacity of quality educational services, continuing the policy of training highly qualified personnel in line with modern needs of the labor market. issues such as the introduction of international standards for assessing the quality of education and training. This indicates the relevance of the topic.

In order to achieve this goal, the "National Training Program" has been adopted and is being successfully implemented.

During the probationary period, first of all, more attention is paid to the student, his in-class and out-of-class academic work, the difficulties he faces, his skills, activities, abilities and methods of studying the laws of development. science is being transformed into the science of teacher and student labor. Second, in the process of education, the tasks of developing the child's thinking ability, independence and mental activity in the learning process are addressed. Third, in addition to inspections of the existing education system, inspections are also being conducted to address the challenges of teaching prospects. Thus, as a science, the methodology of teaching the mother tongue is its own subject, task, theoretical and scientific field, and it has a certain place among a number of disciplines. This science, like other sciences, is evolving and evolving.

As the head of our state noted, "For us, it is a task that will never lose its relevance and importance. .

Language plays an important role in the formation and construction of ideas, the expression of impressions, feelings and experiences. Language is a tool for community members to interact with each other. The more refined this tool is, the clearer, more impressive the idea will be. The need for in-depth study of the mother tongue in school stems from these basic functions of language.

Literacy classes are one of the best ways to improve your reading performance. Classroom and extracurricular reading lessons are directly related to the sections of all subject programs taught in the elementary grades. Finding fiction books based on the

topics covered in the reading lessons, writing the names of the protagonists, describing the ulama, creative drawing, memorizing the appropriate proverbs to complete the idea is an important methodological resource, to determine their didactic basis. is the subject of death.

Essay is a creative work: it requires activity, interest and feedback from the student. All complex tasks such as preparing the material, arranging it, thinking about the composition and plan of the essay, defining the logical connection, choosing the word, phrase, composing and linking the sentence, checking the spelling o It requires the student to use his mental power to the fullest, as well as the ability to manage his own spiritual activities.

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At all stages of the school's development, special attention was paid to the children's independent story-essay. It has become even more important as schools move into a new program designed to improve students' speech, mental and creative development.

In the process of teaching oral and written essays, students need to understand and cover the topic, subordinate their essay to a clear idea, collect material, organize and place it, plan and write according to the plan, the content and the situation of speech. the use of appropriate language tools, the ability to improve written writing. In addition, there are "technical" tasks, such as spelling rules and spelling, punctuation, and margins.

One of the most important requirements for elementary school mother tongue lessons is to work on developing students 'skills in shaping their knowledge so that they are conscious of the knowledge, to get the students used to thinking through each task.

Although the importance of practical work in school is correctly assessed by students, it is difficult to apply students 'theoretical knowledge in practice. They rarely use grammar rules when doing written work. In fact, copying and practical exercises play an important role in improving spelling literacy.

Psychological research shows that spelling literacy is formed gradually. Even in the transition from practical work to the rule, the process of mastering is slow. Initially, it is discussed orally under the guidance of a teacher.

Gradually, students begin to think and reason. In all writing classes, students can improve their spelling literacy by emphasizing the rules of correct writing and doing practical work.

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